

MEDICAL SCIENCES

BASIC REQUIREMENTS AND PRINCIPLES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF EFFECTIVE AND SAFE PROBIOTICS – LACTOBACILLI

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Abstract

The lactobacilli are nowadays the most widely used probiotics. They can have different sources: fermented milk products, fermented vegetables, feces of animals or healthy human etc. Most of them possess a very high activity to the pathogens and it allows to use the instead of the antibiotic. Other strains can modulate innate immune response of the gut immune system. In some publication the authors show anticancer and anti-inflammation activity of the lactobacilli or their metabolites. The hundreds of new strains are described every year? But not all of them are safe an equally effective. **The aim of the work** was the describing the basic requirements and principles for the development of effective and safe lactobacilli isolated out of different sources.

Keywords: lactobacilli, development, basic requirements, effectiveness.

Introduction

The term "dysbacteriosis" was first put into the medicine in 1916 by A. Nissle to designate changes in microbiota of the host (human or animal) after and/or under the influence of various factors. The same term was used by the Soviet microbiologist Bondarenko V.M. and his school in the 80s years of the last century. Later it was shown that the changing community of microorganisms (microbiome) includes not only bacteria, but viruses, fungi and protozoa, that is why the term "dysbacteriosis" was replaced by "dysbiosis". The most studied part of the whole microbiota is the microbiota of gut-intestinal tract, structurally and functionally connected with the skin, genitourinary and respiratory systems microbiota. Despite the rather aggressive attitude of supporters of the secondary nature of changes microbiota, just in the last decades of the 20th century Russian school of microbiologists has already formulated and proved the main principles of the theory of microbiota- host interaction as well as the role of probiotics for the prevention and correction of the serious host's organism pathologies, bacterial translocation pathways with subsequent carriage and inflammation in lungs, liver and so on [1,2] long before other researchers had confirmed the theory about the leading role of microflora, described the presence of axes “gut-brain” [3], “gut-lungs” [4], “gut-liver” [5] and so on. The decades of the investigation of the probiotic properties had shown that not all strains of *Lactobacilli*, *E. coli* and *Enterococci* can be universally useful for every person or animal (if we are talking about veterinary medicine and animal husbandry). Commercially available lactobacilli strains may have antagonistic effects not only on

pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microorganisms, but also on indigene lactobacilli of the consumer [6]. So there is a necessity for preparation of personal probiotic based on lactobacilli, biocompatible with the resident lactobacilli of the patient and/or capable suppress unwanted microbiota.

The effects of probiotic, according to FAO/WHO (2001), are strain-specific and cannot be of a “general nature.” Different strains only provide their own probiotic effect. Therefore, it is necessary to very clearly monitor the characteristics, properties and performance indicators of each specific strain (for example, the LGG® strain, and not just *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*). The most investigated LGG® was isolated from a fecal sample of a healthy adult male in 1985. The strain was specifically selected as having optimal characteristics for its effect on human health [7]. A number of case reports describe episodes of infection caused by organisms consistent with probiotic strains in patients who consumed probiotics prior to symptom onset. Several cases of bacteremia associated with *Lactobacilli* have been reported, including *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, and *Lactobacillus GG* [8-13]. Endocarditis events due to *Lactobacillus* have been reported [14]. The development of an abscess associated with *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* was also reported twice [15,16].

The aim of the work is the describing the basic requirements and principles for the development of effective and safe lactobacilli isolated out of different sources. The effective and safe probiotic should successfully cooperate with the host's “useful” microbiota

and suppress pathogens. The profit of the possibility to adhere to the wall of the gut is discussed.

The basic requirements for Lactobacilli strains isolation

The first stage in the development and creation of probiotic strains is the isolation and identification the strains as Lactobacilli. The source of them is very important for the safe use as a possible probiotic strain. The method of the selection is described is described for example in [17]. The most popular media is MRS culture medium was designed for isolation and cultivation of lactobacilli by De Man, Rogosa and Sharpe in 1960. Other diagnostic culture media for isolation and cultivation of lactobacilli are the variants of the MRS. Others use the natural substrates for the growth of lactobacilli without any toxic components. For example the media can consist only of skimmed milk, 5% yeast extract and 2,5% agar. During the personal use such medias are better because there is no necessity to sediment the bacilli and dilute them again in NaCl. For the experimental aims it is possible to use any of the available media, but the control group should receive the adequate solution by the same way of the use. The sources can be different: for example in [17] the strains were isolated from fermented dates or grapes, from breast milk, and from infant feces. In our work we used the human or domestic animals feces, homemade fermented cabbages or cucumbers, homemade fermented milk products. After the isolation the Gram staining and catalase test on the isolates should confirm that the strains are probably lactic acid bacteria (LAB). A rapid screening for acid and bile tolerance should be carried out. All these tests are cheap and allow to avoid the undesirable mistakes and unwanted expenses. If the strains exhibited growth of over 80% at pH 3 and 0.3% ox bile and 1.9 mg/mL pancreatic enzymes for 3 h, they can be further identified using 16 S rRNA gene sequences.

The study of the isolated bacterial strains properties

The study the properties of the isolated bacterial culture is the second stage. The requirements for the assessment of the effectiveness and safety of lactobacilli as probiotics are presented in WHO guidelines and government guidelines and guidelines. In particular, in the Russian Federation, researchers must use the methods recommended by the Guidelines for sanitary and epidemiological assessment of the safety and functional potential of probiotic microorganisms used for food production [18]. According to this document, among other things all strains should be studied for survival in the proximal gastrointestinal tract and proliferation in the large intestine, resistance to gastric acidity, bile, adhesion to human epithelial cells and cell cultures, antagonistic activity against pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms that cause acute intestinal infections and others infections, the ability to hydrolyze bile acids and the ability to reduce the adhesion of opportunistic microbes in the intestine. So, the selection of strain is based on the study of several properties, confirmed their possibility to be used:

- the strain should be active against pathogenic microbiota;

- its antagonistic activity should be minimal for the indigene lactobacilli;

- the probiotic strain should demonstrate the ability to compete with pathogenic and opportunistic bacteria for adhesion sites;

- it should stay in the gut during the long period of time after the use, so it should have satisfactory adhesive properties

A pronounced antagonistic activity against pathogenic microorganisms

The concept of antagonistic activity is very broad and consists of many components, including a higher rate of bacterial reproduction, a wider set of enzymes, as well as the production of various bactericidal and bacteriostatic substances [19,20]. Among these substances, organic fatty acids have a high antagonistic activity against pathogens. In particular, lactobacilli are capable of synthesizing natural antibiotic-like substances named bacteriocins [21,22]. Bacteriocins produced by lactobacilli inhibit the reproduction of a wide range of microorganisms: Clostridium, Streptococci, Enterobacteria, Listeria, Candida, etc. [23]. Some strains of *L. paracasei*, *L. fermentum*, and *L. rhamnosus* showed antimicrobial activity against *C. albicans*. [17]. This inhibitory effect on pathogenic microorganisms is related to various bacteriocins, through metabolites produced by *Lactobacillus* spp. [24,25]. The antagonistic activity of lactobacilli is possible to determine by different approach. To detect the antibacterial activity against indicator bacteria (*S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *E. coli*), a spot-on-the-lawn assay was carried out with some modification [26]. Briefly, each indicator bacterium was incubated in 5 mL brain heart infusion (BHI) broth at 35 °C overnight. Moreover, 50 µL of the culture was added to 5 mL of BHI soft agar (0.7% agar), and this mixture was poured onto BHI agar. The tested LAB strains were grown in BHI broth for 48 h, and the supernatants were collected by centrifugation at 8000× g at 4 °C for 10 min. The collected supernatants were adjusted to pH 6.0 with NaOH, treated with or without heating at 80 °C for 10 min, filtered using a 0.2-µm filter, 10 µL of the samples were then spotted onto BHI soft-agar plates containing the indicator bacterium. The plates were analyzed for bacterial growth inhibition after incubation at 35 °C for 18 h.

For example, to determine the antagonistic activity of *Lactobacillus* strains, isolated from the gastrointestinal tract of healthy people, in relation to the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strain co-cultivation and diffusion into agar using wells were used. [27].

During co-cultivation *lactobacilli* and *K. pneumoniae* in equal doses were added to MRS broth and incubated at a temperature of 37±1 °C. The control was a monoculture of *K. pneumoniae* grown under the same conditions. After 24 and 48 hours of incubation, *K. pneumoniae* cells grown in monoculture and in co-cultivation with lactobacilli on solid agar were counted.

To study the antagonistic activity of *Lactobacillus* by agar diffusion method, the strains were incubated in MRS broth at a temperature of 37 ± 1 °C. containing *K. pneumoniae* at a concentration of 106 CFU/cm³ was added to solid agar and was put onto Petri dishes. After

the agar solidified, wells with a diameter of 5 mm were prepared with a sterile instrument, into which 50 μm^3 of the test samples were added. The results were taken into account after 24 and 48 hours of incubation at 37 ± 1 °C. They have found by both methods that high antagonistic activity of the *L. rhamnosus* F strain but antagonistic activity of the *L. helveticus* NK1 strain was insignificant [27].

The antagonistic activity of lactobacilli can be also determined by the method of delayed antagonism using double-layer agar. In [17] different strains of *Lactobacillus* were co-cultivated with *C. albicans*. It was shown that the mycelial growth of *C. albicans* was delayed and biofilm formation was inhibited. In addition, the expression of biofilm-specific genes was reduced too. In addition, *Lactobacillus* strains exhibited an antagonistic activity against pathogenic microorganisms *Enterococcus faecium*, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *E. coli*, *Helicobacter pylori*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Propionibacterium acnes*, *Shigella sonnei*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, and the activity was strain dependent. Besides the direct bactericide activity lactobacilli produce the metabolites which downward the pH of the environment. It provides a mediated effect on the enzymatic activity of pathogens.

The absence or minimal antagonistic activity for the indigene lactobacilli

The used strains should not inhibit the growth of indigenous microbiota. It was previously shown that the pharmacy probiotics, designed on the basis of the allogenic strains, can displace the indigenes strains of the host and induce the inflammation in the gut.

The determination of the ability of probiotic strains inhibit representatives of normal intestinal flora *in vitro* should be realized simultaneously by two methods: perpendicular streaks and by plaque leakage. The test culture should be sowing in the form of a streak along the diameter onto a Petri cup with an optimal nutrient medium. Perpendiculars to the first seeding, streaks of other studied microorganisms are made. In the other case a daily broth culture of the microorganisms is applied to the nutrient medium using a loop. After drying, apply a drop of another test culture in a loop nearby at a distance of 0.5 cm so that the second drop flows onto the first to the middle and dry. After the cultivation at 37 °C for 24 - 48 hours the accounting for results by the measure the zone of growth inhibition of crops is realized. When inoculating the studied and test cultures of microorganisms using perpendicular streaks, their influence on each other can be revealed. In case of antagonism, after a day of co-cultivation, zones of growth inhibition will be observed. In this case the use of the tested strain is not possible even all other properties are satisfactory.

The adhesive properties of lactobacilli

It is believed that the ability of probiotic strains to bind to certain receptors on the surface of the gastrointestinal mucosa provides competition for these receptors with pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms, since the number of such receptors on epithelial cells is limited. This is confirmed by observations indicating that pretreatment of targets with Cohn lectin or bacterial adhesives drastically reduces the number of

microorganisms that can fix on the preliminary incubated cells. It is believed also that adherent probiotic bacteria "block" eukaryotic cell receptors, making them unavailable for binding to pathogenic agents. So the value of adhesive strains for creating probiotic drugs lies not only in their ability to long-term persistence in the gastrointestinal tract, but also in competition with pathogens for adhesion sites on the surface of enterocytes. A number of studies have shown that the oral administration of lactobacilli with distinct adhesion leads to a significant decrease in the number of *E. coli* colonizing the intestines of chickens [22, 24]. It was proved that *Lactobacillus* species with probiotic property can be used in poultry feed formulation for their health benefit to combat gastrointestinal infections. [28]. It was shown that bacteria of the genus *Lactobacillus* can prevent colonization of the vaginal epithelium by *Ps. aeruginosa*, *Enterococcus sp.*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *E. coli* [29], it also binds glycolipid receptors of *Helicobacter pylori* [30]. The reduced adhesion of intestinal pathogens, carrying S-fimbria on their surface, when using *Lactobacillus* had been also shown [31]. From the other side, the study of adhesive properties of strains on cell models Caco-2 and T84 intestinal epithelial cells (IECs) under a variety of physiological conditions has discovered unexpected properties of two popular lactobacillus strains—*Lacticaseibacillus paracasei* BL23 and *Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus* GG. They are very closely related species, yet with differential features. *L. rhamnosus* is a probiotic species widely studied in clinical trials for the treatment and/or prevention of various health conditions such as, ulcerative colitis [32], diarrhea [33, 34] and atopic dermatitis [35]. The internalization of those strains occurred at a variable rate that depends on the bacterial strain and IEC line, and the most efficient was BL23 internalization by IECs T84. Efficient internalization required active IEC proliferation, as it improved naturally at the early confluence stages and by stimulation with epidermal growth factor (EGF). Bacterial uptake required actin polymerization, as shown by cytochalasin D inhibition, and it was partially bound to clathrin and caveolin dependent endocytosis. Bacteria remained viable inside the IEC for as long as 72 h without damaging the epithelial cells, and paracellular transcytosis was observed. So, the internalization of commensal bacteria is a natural, nonpathogenic process that may be relevant in crosstalk processes between the intestinal populations and the host [36]. So the adhesive properties of lactobacillus are still need to be explored more deeply.

These properties of lactobacilli are studied using two methods. In the first method, a direct reaction of the anti-adhesive activity of cultures is used, in the second - an indirect reaction, using supernatants of lactobacilli cultures. Direct anti-adhesive activity of lactobacilli is studied on human erythrocytes using cultures of lactobacilli and cultures of test strains. In the preparations, the number of test cultures attached to 50 red blood cells in one field of view is counted. In parallel, the number of microorganisms attached to erythrocytes in a parallel sample, to which cultures of lactobacilli were not added, is counted. Compare the data obtained and record the results as percentages. If the number of

cells of the test strain attached to 50 red blood cells mixed with cultures of lactobacilli is less than in a pure sample, it is believed that the cultures of lactobacilli have anti-adhesive properties. The indirect reaction is the modified direct method with the use of the supernatant of the strains instead of the culture of the lactobacilli. Some researcher interprets the ability of probiotic to adhere to epithelial cells in vitro as a marker of pathogenicity.

Adhesion to the intestinal mucosa and extracellular matrix proteins is a first step in the pathogenesis of many microbes [37]. They have found the difference between *Lactobacillus GG*-like isolates from cases of bacteremia and the original *Lactobacillus GG* strain [38]. The in vitro adhesion rate to human intestinal mucus, collagen, and fibrinogen of 3 of the tested clinical isolates was different from that of the original *Lactobacillus GG* strain. These same 3 isolates exhibited a significantly higher adhesion rate than the original strain.

From the other side, many surface layer proteins are involved in host adhesion, and play significant role in the modification of some signaling pathways within the host cells and realization of the positive properties of lactobacilli. [39]. Most of authors affirm that adherence of beneficial bacteria to the intestinal mucosa is considered important for exerting their function and is a claimed key characteristic of probiotic [40, 41] In vitro studies analyze adherence of probiotic bacteria to

- mucin adsorbed onto abiotic surfaces (e.g., polystyrene)[42],

- confluent intestinal cell layer cultures (HT-29, HT-29-MTX and Caco-2 are customary cell lines used in adhesion assays) in cell/tissue culture plates, or iii) extracellular matrix components such as fibronectin and collagen [43]. Bacterial adhesion processes can be mediated by physico-chemical forces such as hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions via lipoteichoic acids or surface proteins [40,41,44]. Bacterial aggregation is connected with the adhesive ability [45] and claimed a desirable characteristic of probiotics, since aggregated bacteria inhibited adhesion of pathogenic bacteria [46]. Several *L. acidophilus* surface proteins including the surface layer protein SlpA have been identified as potential adhesive molecules by proteome analysis using 2-DE and mass spectrometry and by comparison of strains with high and low adhesive capacity to Caco-2 intestinal cells [47]. The adhesive properties of lactobacilli can be determined on human erythrocytes 0 (1) group Rn+ (RBC) [48], epithelial cells of the oral mucosa and the HEP 2 cell line [49] and on enterocytes of the small intestine of piglet embryos [49].

In the experiments of Kozlovsky et al [50] adhesive properties of lactobacilli were studied in vitro on the model of formalinized red blood cells (RBC) by V. Brilis (1984) [51] with some modification. The bacterial suspensions at a concentration of 2×10^9 CFU / ml, RBC at a concentration of 2×10^8 cells / ml were used. The concentration of RBC was calculated in the Goryaev's chamber under a light microscopy. The concentration of microbial cell suspension was determined by the optical density at 560 nm. 0,5 ml of a suspension of RBC and microbial cells was mixed, incubated for

45 minutes at 37°C, periodically shaking. The drop of suspension was put on the object-plate for getting thin film, dried and painted with Romanovsky-Gimza dye. The mean value of adhesion index was determined by the average number of microbes adhering to the surface of one red blood cell. All available erythrocytes in 5 visual fields were counted, but not less than 50 cells. The percentage of red blood cells with bacterial cells on their surfaces (adhesion index) was calculated in relation to the total number of erythrocytes taken into account (K%). Between 206 strain, isolated out of the different sources almost all strains had the ability to adhere to RBC. The highest values of adhesion index and K% were determined for the strains taken out of animals gastrointestinal tract. The strains related to the lumen and wall microbiota practically did not differ in their adhesive properties.

Strains isolated from cultured milk foods and plant fermentation products have shown a low adhesive activity, the ability to adhere significantly differed in groups depending on their origin.

Conclusion

The new strain of any of the probiotic lactobacilli should be effective, safe and personally oriented. There is a lot of necessary examination of new strains, and the final decision of the use should be based on the personal sensitivity of the customer and the properties of the strain proved by the preliminary investigation. The design of new effective and safe probiotics on the basis of lactobacilli should use the biotic sources, microbes must be friendly to indigene lactobacilli and active against pathogens and opportunistic infections and possess a good adhesive properties. There are a lot of questions in the field of probiotic use, but there is no the common strategy for their usefulness confirmation. In any case, the safety is the most important aspect of the probiotic treating.

Conflict of the interests The Authors declare about the absence of any conflict in any of the part of the investigation

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